

DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF SOIL TREATMENT BEFORE PLANTING

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Increasing productivity is the main factor in raising the production of agricultural products to a higher level.

Soil tillage technology is the main factor in the set of complex mechanized agrotechnical activities that ensure productivity increase.

Quality soil treatment means creating favorable conditions for chemical, physical and microbiological processes in the soil. This, in turn, increases the influence of mineral fertilizers applied to the soil, irrigation and other agrotechnical measures. In addition, conditions are created for the operation of planting, inter-row processing and harvesting machines at the level of demand. This leads to increased labor productivity, saving fuel and water consumption [1,2,3,5,6].

The analysis of the results of several scientific researches shows that the yield of cotton and other agricultural crops increases by 20...25% with the improvement of the quality of tillage [7,8].

Considering that tillage technology is the most energy-intensive in agricultural production, and according to the results of several studies, 50-60% of the total energy used in the cultivation of agricultural crops is spent on tillage. If we take this indicator on the scale of the Republic, it means that several thousand plows, deep looseners, chisel-cultivators, toothed and disk harrows, land levelers and other tools are used [9,10,11].

High-quality cultivation of soil with minimum energy consumption depends to a large extent on the improvement of the technological process and the construction of soil-cultivating machines and working bodies.

Tillage machines and tools used in agricultural production cannot be said to be up to date. Most of them do not fully meet agrotechnical requirements due to high energy consumption and low productivity [12,13,14,15,16].

Due to the implementation of the plowing process, which is considered as the primary and main tillage of the soil, with the help of various types of plows, the irregularities created in the field lead to an increase in the amount of energy spent at the expense of the agricultural machines and technical means used to eliminate them. In pre-sowing tillage, it was observed that soil structure, physical-chemical and technological properties were adversely affected due to

entering and exiting a separate field with the help of special machines during each technological process [17,18,19,20].

A number of scientific researches have shown that loosening the tillage layer without removing it to the soil surface in different soil and climatic conditions is an agrotechnical method that ensures an increase in cotton productivity.

Academic M. V. Muhammadjanov's research showed that the yield increased by 2.5...5.4 c/h in a field plowed at a depth of 30 cm with loosening of the soil at a depth of 50 cm [13,14,21,22,23].

It can be seen from the results of several researches that the increase in productivity with softening of the soil layer is mainly due to the improvement of the water-air regime in the soil layer, better development of plant roots, strengthening of microbiological processes, and better use of the supply elements in the soil layers. The table below analyzes the increase in productivity due to loosening the soil layer without removing it to the surface [2,5,23].

Effect of soil softening on cotton yield.

(Information of M.V. Muhammadjonov)

Table № 1.

Experiment option	Years			Productivity, centner/hectare	
	I	II	III	average	the addition of
30 cm deep plowing	34,3	34,54	33,1	33,98	0
50 cm deep loosening with 30 cm deep plowing	36,8	39,98	38,4	38,39	4,41

The driving layer is softened by two different technologies:

- after driving;
- until driving.

A. R. According to Rahmonov's information, it is advisable to make the soil layer after plowing. The obtained results are reflected in Table 2 [17,18,19,21].

That the soil is treated according to different technologies effect on productivity.

(Information of A. R. Rahmonov)

Table № 2.

Experiment option	Years			Productivity, centner/hectare	
	I	II	III	average	the addition of
30 cm. deep autumn plowing	18,6	19,2	19,3	19,0	0
28...30 cm. with autumn plowing at a depth of 50 cm. softening in depth	23,9	23,4	24,2	23,8	4,8
50 cm. 28...30 cm with softening in depth. deep autumn plowing	23,7	23,2	23,5	23,5	4,5

The analysis of the obtained results shows that it is rational to soften the soil layer after plowing based on agrotechnical, energy and economic indicators.

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